

TWINNED
By Stars

D5.4 REPORT ON D&C ACTIVITIES 2
WP5 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

TWINNEDBYSTARS

UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF INNOVATION, CIRCULARITY, AND
DIGITALISATION FOR ACCELERATING NEW MARINE-BASED
ECOTOURISM, JOINT PRACTICES, AND BUSINESSES IN ORS

GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101124900

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¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive

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Acronyms & abbreviations

D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EC	European Commission
CE	Consulta Europa
EU	European Union
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package
T.no	Task
R&I	Research and Innovation

1. Executive summary

TWINNEDbySTARS seeks to enhance the competitiveness of the maritime tourism sector in Outermost Regions while contributing to the protection of marine biodiversity, preserving cultural heritage, and developing marine astro tourism by highlighting ancient navigational routes as sustainable destinations for these remote areas. Additionally, the project aims to strengthen existing partnerships, build capacity, and co-create tourism products.

To achieve these goals, TWINNEDbySTARS plans to engage stakeholders at regional, national, and European levels through an inclusive process. The initiative will priorities the involvement of key sectors, including industry (especially businesses within the nautical value and supply chain in participating regions), civil society (such as sailors' and consumers' associations), public administrations (including tourist boards), and academia.

This report, part of Work Package 5, summaries the communication actions and activities carried out during the first two years of the project (M1/October 2023–M24/September 2025). It also serves as a reference for reviewing and refining the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) strategy for the last period of the project (M25-M36). A final version of this report is due at M35, summarizing all results and achievements of WP5 by the end of the project.

Finally, notable achievements include the project's presence at international events, recognition by the funding entity CINEA in their online publications, and even feature in their videos on YouTube.

This is a public document that will be available on the official project website, upon approval: www.twinnedbystars.eu.

2. Introduction

This document presents the dissemination and communication activities carried out during the first two years (M1 - M24) in the framework of the TWINNEDbySTARS project. The project, which aims to turn the European Outermost Regions (ORs) into an internationally recognised maritime ecotourism destination, has prioritised effective communication of its progress and results. Dissemination actions have been also essential to increase the visibility of the project, engage stakeholders and encourage the adoption of good practices related to marine biodiversity conservation, climate change mitigation and astro-tourism.

Throughout this period, communication and dissemination strategies have been implemented targeting both specialised and general audiences, using a variety of channels and tools.

2.1 Project background

TWINNEDbySTARS aims to merge tourism, marine biodiversity conservation, climate change mitigation, and astrotourism to turn the European ORs into a prestigious maritime ecotourism destination. TWINNEDbySTARS promotes ecotourism through on-board marine education, courteous navigation, and unique experiences that reinforce responsible behaviour, building on previous initiatives in the Macaronesian region. The project fosters digital and ecological innovation, strengthens partnerships, and opens doors for co-creation. With the support of experienced experts in the nautical tourism industry, it involves public and private entities in a phased process that starts with preliminary analysis, mapping, and training definition and continues with training implementation, marketing, and product testing.

Partner No.	Participant organisation name	Acronym	Country
1	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	ULPGC-TIDES	ES
1.1	Fundación Canaria Parque Científico Tecnológico de la ULPGC	FCPCT/ULPGC	ES
2	Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation	CE	ES
3	Asociación Cluster Marítimo de Canarias	CMC	ES
4	Océano de Experiencias SL	NAUTIC OCEAN	ES
5	Centro Tecnológico de Ciencias Marinas	CETECIMA	ES
6	Associação MarinaFunchal	MARINA FUNCHAL	PT
7	Associação Comercial E Industrial Do Funchal	ACIF-CCIM	PT
8	Secretaria Regional do Mar e das Pescas	DRPM AZORES	PT
9	Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique	CTM	FR
10	European Boating Industry	EBI	BE

Table 1. TWINNEDbySTARS consortium.

2.2 Objectives of the D&C report

This report serves as a project activity monitoring enabling the assessment of whether planned actions are being executed correctly and on schedule, as well as their effectiveness. This process allows for the refinement of the communication and dissemination plan to enhance its reach and impact.

This document is designed to disseminate and transfer the outcomes and results of all TWINNEDbySTARS activities to key stakeholders. The specific objectives are:

1. To enhance the project's visibility and raise awareness among the general public.
2. To facilitate stakeholder engagement.
3. To support knowledge transfer through both scientific and non-scientific publications, as well as the organisation of training events.
4. To establish connections with a broad network of EU projects (sister projects) and initiatives, enabling the exchange of experiences and the promotion of R&I activities.
5. To ensure effective internal communication among partners and monitor their activities.

Task title		Task description
T5.1	Development of the D&C Plan	A Dissemination & Communication (D&C) Plan will be developed at M3 detailing target groups to be reached, communication channels, tools, and outputs to be used, and providing a calendar of D&C activities. The Plan will be periodically updated.
T5.2	Dissemination activities	A variety of materials and tools will be produced including the project website, logo and corporate image, layout, posters and roll-ups as well as banners for social media. It will also deal with the dissemination and promotion of the organised events, webinars, workshops and trainings from T5.3 as well as with other funded projects.
T5.3	Awareness raising activities and outreach to society	This task deals with the organisation of events, webinars, workshops, trainings or other dissemination actions.

Table 2. WP5 tasks' descriptions.

During the first year of the project, WP5 has worked in close synergy with WP1 and WP2. The deliverable "D1.1 Stakeholder Engagement Plan," submitted in M11 (August 2024), has served as a key reference for planning and implementing D&C actions under WP5. In this sense, numerous emails targeting specific regional, national, and EU stakeholders have been sent to inform them about the project and invite them to join the TWINNEDbySTARS network. Additionally, several social media campaigns have been designed, and various consortium partners have actively participated in events at the European level to further attract companies to the project. Likewise, WP5 has played a significant role in advancing WP2, which aims to increase awareness, motivation, and skills and provide tools to tourism firms and decision-makers in the

context of coastal and maritime tourism. Under WP2, dedicated mailing campaigns and promotional actions were executed in order to reach out to potential maritime and nautical companies in order to

During the second year of the project, WP5 worked in close cooperation with WP3 to promote and recruit participants for the co-creation workshops organised under Task 3.2 and later on to give wide visibility to the results of the voting process and the launch of the selected product under Task 3.4. WP5 played a key role in disseminating the collaborative tourism products created in the workshops through dedicated sections on the website, social media campaigns, newsletters and press releases, ensuring broad outreach across the four regions.

In parallel, WP5 has supported WP2 in the promotion of the training and capacity building programme for enterprises, particularly under Task 2.2. This has included targeted email campaigns, online news articles, and visibility actions for both the AI digital communication courses and the Marine Starlight certification trainings, contributing to a strong participation of SMEs and reinforcing the project’s positioning as a driver of skills, innovation and sustainability in the Outermost Regions.

2.3 Target groups

Similarly, a stakeholder’s identification process has been carried out through different tasks within this reports time framework, mainly at WP1 and WP5. For this purpose, a mapping of actors (task 1.1) of the quadruple helix and a Stakeholder Engagement Plan has been previously conducted to ensure a wide representation of these stakeholders as target groups in the communication and dissemination actions within the project. The stakeholder’s engagement tasks will remain active during the whole life of the project.

TWINNEDbySTARS is targeting representatives of the Quadruple Helix Model recognising four major actors in the innovation system:

TARGET GROUP	DESCRIPTION
Science stakeholders	Includes a diverse network of actors managing, coordinating, or conducting scientific research related to greening activities and innovation. This group brings in the research community, science managers as well students and PhD scientists at local, national, intergovernmental, and EU levels as well as representatives of other EU projects.
Policy makers	Representatives of private or public institutions of local, national and global governance, promotion, environmental management and regulation of tourism and nautical activities. Directorates-General (RTD, CLIMA, ENER, ENV, MARE), the JRC, European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency; the European Parliament (intergroups, committees, MEPs), international Ocean governance initiatives, OECD Ocean Economy working group.
Industry	All companies related to nautical and marine tourism. It includes those offering sports and recreational activities at sea. It also includes enterprises selling nautical equipment, charter services, whale watching, nautical schools, and the ports and marinas offering berths and other services to yachts.

Society/public	Citizen science activities will be promoted as for the first group, environmental organisations, local action groups, and other type of associations will be reached to provide them with comprehensive information on TWINNEDbySTARS solutions and to foster social acceptance.
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Table 3. Target groups description.

3. Methodology

At TWINNEDbySTARS, an extensive communication and dissemination strategy has been put in place to engage both the public and key target groups, including marine and maritime businesses, associations, academia and other interested parties.

To facilitate monitoring, partners are required to submit semesterly reports using a D&C template (see Figure 1 below). These reports cover activities such as events organised, social media outreach, news/press releases published, and presentations at conferences. Meanwhile, CE is responsible for monitoring website usage, social media engagement, and events organised under its purview. By analysing these reports, CE can provide recommendations to optimise future dissemination and communication efforts, ensuring a more targeted and effective approach.

Press Releases							
Reporting period	Publisher	Publication date	Title	Location	Link	Outreach	Observations
RP1							

Figure 1. Dissemination and Communication Template.

The main channels for TWINNEDbySTARS dissemination and communication actions are the following:

1) Website:

The website serves as a central platform for disseminating information related to the project. It includes project information, news & events, public project deliverables, newsletter, and multimedia resources. The website is regularly updated to reflect project developments and ensure clear communication with the project’s online wider audience. The TWINNEDbySTARS website was launched in January 2024, and it can be accessed by visiting <https://twinnedbystars.eu/>.

2) Newsletter:

The WP5 leader distributes a regular newsletter to keep subscribers informed about project progress, upcoming events, research results, collaboration opportunities and next steps in the project. This newsletter is emailed to website subscribers, including project partners, marine and maritime companies and stakeholders. The newsletter is also available on the website. The first TWINNEDbySTARS newsletters was distributed on 23 February 2024, the second on 26 September 2024, the third on 25 February 2025 and the fourth on 26 September 2025. These newsletters are made available at <https://twinnedbystars.eu/newsletters/> after being sent to subscribers.

3) LinkedIn:

LinkedIn is being used to reach out to professionals and companies in the nautical and maritime sector. This platform allows sharing of project updates, activities, project meetings, ecotourism or boating special dates or events, and networking opportunities. The profile is available at <https://www.linkedin.com/company/twinned-by-stars/posts/?feedView=all>

4) Facebook:

Facebook is used to reach a wider and more diverse audience. Project updates, videos, infographics and testimonials are posted. Facebook's interactive options, such as commenting and sharing, allows to better understand and connect with the audience. The account is available at: <https://www.facebook.com/twinnedbystars>.

5) Instagram:

Instagram is a more visual communication platform that allows sharing photos, short videos and stories that promote the project's activities, outreach campaigns, events and important moments. This platform is a perfect way to attract the attention of the public and encourage interest in the project's initiatives. It can be visited at <https://www.instagram.com/twinnedbystars/>.

6) X:

This channel is important for the project as it acts as a dynamic platform for real-time communication, engagement and information dissemination. Through X it is possible to reach a wider audience, share project updates, highlight key milestones and interact with stakeholders during various online campaigns and initiatives. The use of X within the project ensures that TWINNEDbySTARS' progress and achievements are accessible, timely and widely disseminated. Posts are available via <https://x.com/TwinnedbyStars>.

7) YouTube:

The TWINNEDbySTARS YouTube channel serves as a central hub for video content related to the project, with the project promotional video and recorded webinars/actions providing an in-depth view of the work being done. Thanks to its broad reach and engaging format, YouTube allows to connect with and inform the public effectively, as demonstrated by the inaugural video, the 'Star Tour' webinar and the official animated video of the project, both released in 2024.

Access to <https://www.youtube.com/@twinnedbystars> to visit the channel.

8) External Platforms:

By strategically combining the above communication channels, the reach and impact of different messages is maximised across different audience segments, fostering engagement and collaboration with marine and maritime businesses and various stakeholders. In addition, since the beginning of the project, the EU Survey and Google Forms have been used to gather targeted feedback through tailored forms, for the stakeholder engagement activities, which were distributed to stakeholders and shared through social media platforms for increased visibility.

Particularly, two surveys in cooperation with WP2 have been developed to engage and collect feedback from ORs' companies in order to share next project activities. The links to these surveys have been shared on social networks to increase their visibility and consequently increase participation.

Table below includes the links to access to the surveys and other forms created:

Survey	Link	Type of survey
EU Survey	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/TWINNEDbySTARSQuestionnaire	This questionnaire was created to involve companies in the project.
	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/twinned-for-smes	This questionnaire was developed to gather information on the activity, needs and challenges of companies to help share WP2 and WP3 activities.

Table 4. Links to the EU Survey Forms

4. Dissemination & communication activities

4.1 Visual identity

The TWINNEDbySTARS logo is a visual representation that summarises the scope and values of the project. Its main design is a right-facing sailboat, representing the fundamental elements that define the project's mission: progress and innovation. The idea of constantly moving forward and exploring new opportunities is strengthened by the sailboat's forward motion.

The logo also has four stars representing the outermost areas of the project. Finally, a circle connects these components, which strengthens the notion of cohesion and unity between the different areas. The circle serves as a symbol of integration and connectivity, concepts essential to the goal of the TWINNEDbySTARS project.

Figure 2. TWINNEDbySTARS's logotype.

The logo uses the shades of navy blue and red, which are characteristic of the world of the sea. These colours not only reinforce the maritime theme of the project, but also evoke the qualities of stability, confidence (blue) and dynamism (red). These qualities are essential to represent an innovative and constantly developing project.

The main typeface of the TWINNEDbySTARS project is Montserrat, a typeface that adds modernity, legibility and professionalism to the visual design. Montserrat's geometric, sans-serif typeface is ideal for projects that seek to communicate innovation and progress because it increases the sense of clarity and precision. In addition, its clean, contemporary design makes it easy to read in a variety of formats, both digital and print, ensuring that the message is delivered effectively and coherently.

Figure 3. TWINNEDbySTARS' colours and typeface.

This logo was designed using a grid that helps to maintain consistent alignment and proportion in all of its elements. The grid ensures that the main components of the logo, such as the circular icon containing the sail figure, stars and waves, along with the TWINNEDbySTARS text, are well balanced and proportioned. This grid system allows the design to be flexible and scalable, maintaining its visual consistency across different sizes and applications.

As for the minimum safe space, it refers to the area around the logo that must remain free of other visual elements to avoid distractions and ensure that the logo maintains its impact and legibility. The minimum safe space equals one square of the grid on each of the four sides of the logo. This minimum spacing ensures that the logo has sufficient breathing space and does not feel cluttered by other graphics or text.

In addition, a minimum size of 15 mm is set for the logo. This minimum size ensures that all details of the logo, including graphic and typographic elements, remain legible and recognisable, even when reduced to smaller applications of promotional materials.

Figure 4. Representation of the logo grid, the minimum safety space and the maximum reduction size.

The negative version of the logo is essential to ensure the versatility and coherence of the branding in different situations. The negative version of the logo, like the main logo, maintains the essence of the key elements (the sailboat, the stars and the circle), but adapts to different corporate backgrounds, allowing the logo to be legible and have a significant visual impact even in high contrast situations. The logo is presented in white with both a navy blue and red background so that all graphic elements are visible.

Figure 5. Negative version of the logo.

These guidelines have been established to ensure the correct implementation of the logo on all promotional materials. The proper use of the logo ensures that its clarity and visual strength is retained, regardless of the format or medium in which it is applied, from physical print to digital media.

4.2 Promotionals materials

4.2.1 LEAFLET & FLYER

These key promotional materials have been carefully designed to inform the target groups about TWINNEDbySTARS' primary objectives, consortium members, and other relevant details, including how to join the project's networks.

Leaflets and flyers will be distributed by partners during relevant events and meetings, with each partner responsible for printing their copies. These materials will also be available in both digital and printable formats, ensuring broad dissemination through digital channels. The material can be downloaded at <https://twinnedbystars.eu/results/>.

Partners

The **TWINNEDbySTARS** consortium consists of seasoned professionals with extensive experience in nautical tourism, spanning applied and research fields, business support through clusters and chambers of commerce, and regulatory aspects within the public administration sector.

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TWINNEDbySTARS will convert Europe's outermost regions into an internationally recognised maritime ecotourism destination that harnesses the benefits of tourism for marine biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation, such as:

- New products and services integrated into the local and regional tourist offer will be created.
- New tourist routes and new partnerships on the theme will be developed.
- TwinnedByStars will offer new ecotourism packages promoting cross-border and inter-regional cooperation.

Join us in building stronger networks, uplifting industry standards, and creating a shared identity. Together, we empower tourism stakeholders, foster innovation, and co-create unforgettable nautical experiences. From stargazing to eco-friendly journeys, **TWINNEDbySTARS** invites you to be part of an exciting voyage towards a brighter and more sustainable future. Explore the possibilities with us!

Unlocking the potential of innovation, circularity, and digitalisation for accelerating new marine-based ecotourism, joint practices, and businesses in ORs

Want to know more?

Visit: www.twinnedbystars.eu
 Contact us: info@twinnedbystars.eu
 Follow us!

Figure 6. TWINNEDbySTARS's leaflet.

What is TWINNEDbySTARS about?

TWINNEDbySTARS aims to make the outermost regions more visible and well-known in the tourism industry. These regions play a crucial role in supporting EU environmental policies. The project will showcase the innovative potential of tourism in these regions, focusing on aspects like marine biodiversity, cultural heritage, and astrotourism. This will involve creating networks and frameworks for collaborative design and development of a unique marine ecotourism experience centred around navigation and stargazing.

Objectives:

- Strengthening and sustaining cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism within the ORs. This involves linking the quadruple helix and ensuring network homogeneity through the promotion of certifications and promoting a unified brand image.
- Upskilling and capacity building for tourism firms and stakeholders in coastal and maritime tourism (circular economy practices, digital transition, networking and innovation).
- Creating new spaces for the co-creation of innovative products and nautical tourism experiences (star tourism, marine ecotourism, sustainable Atlantic crossing using trade winds, and the application of virtual reality).

Grant agreement number: 101124900
Granting authority: European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
Starting date: 1 October 2023
Project duration: 36 months
Funding rate: 85%
Grant amount: 996,630.11 €

www.twinnedbystars.eu

Methodology:

The viability of the project hinges on the execution of tangible activities involving both public and private entities that collectively represent the quadruple helix of the concerned regions. The envisaged collaboration is well-founded, drawing on the established working relationships among many of the participating entities from prior projects.

In the initial phase, activities such as analysis, mapping, stakeholder engagement, co-creation, and training definition will be implemented. Subsequently, the focus will shift towards training execution, implementation of the marketing and commercialisation plan, and testing of the developed product.

Figure 7. TWINNEDbySTARS's flyer.

4.2.2 ROLL UP

A standardised **roll-up** of 85 cm x 200cm has been designed. It conveys key messages, branding, funding, the EU emblem, and promotional information about the project such as the consortium members, website, QR code and the social media channels. The roll-up is available to be printed and used by every partner to assist any on-site event. This roll-up design may also be used digitally to promote the project on different websites, platforms, digital newspapers and social media channels.

Figure 8. TWINNEDbySTARS's roll-up.

4.2.3 PPT's TEMPLATE

Consulta Europa, as the leader of WP5 – Dissemination and Communication, have elaborated the template of all promotional materials and reporting support documents as, for example, the Power Point Presentation's template or the Deliverable's template.

Figure 9. TWINNEDbySTARS PPT's template.

4.2.4 OTHER PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

Specific events-oriented designs have been also elaborated, as for example the poster for the EU OCEAN DAYS.

Figure 10. EU Ocean Days' poster.

4.3 Website

The TWINNEDbySTARS website (<https://twinnedbystars.eu/>) has been released M3 (December 2023) and filled out with all relevant information about the project and the consortium. Each section is designed to provide stakeholders and the public with comprehensive information about the project's objectives, progress, and achievements:

Join the **TWINNEDbySTARS** network and make a contribution!

Join our crew can benefits you in variety of ways.

Be part of our community!

Upcoming events

17 - 19 / 09 / 2024
ICOE 2024: Uniting Global Ocean Energy Leaders in Melbourne

18 - 22 / 09 / 2024
B&T WEEKS: Unveiling Cutting-Edge Advancements in Marine Science and Technology

20 - 22 / 11 / 2024
Sun&Blue

News

The 'TWINNEDbySTARS' Project at the Olympic Port during the America's Cup 2024

From 22 August to 16 October, the Port Olímpic is witnessing the implementation of the 'TWINNEDbySTARS' project, which is having a special...

Invitation to co-creation workshop for SMEs of the maritime tourism sector in the Canary Islands, Madeira, Azores and Martinique

16 September | 16 August 2024

Successful Completion of the Masterclass Sessions for SMEs in the Maritime Tourism Sector

16 September | 16 July 2024

TWINNEDbySTARS Boosts Astrorism with a Masterclass for SMEs in the Maritime Tourism Sector in the Canary Islands

16 September | 15 June 2024

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TWINNEDbySTARS

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Figure 11. TWINNEDbySTARS's website home page

4.3.1 WEBSITE IMPROVEMENTS

The initial structure of the website was created with the key sections: About, Partners, News & Events, and Contact. These sections provide a solid basis for communicating the project's mission, important partnerships, and latest news, as well as offering an accessible point of contact. Several new sections have been added to this basic structure with the aim of improving the user experience (UX), optimising navigation to make it easier to understand and more fluid. This makes it easier to access the information they are looking for and ensures a more pleasant and effective interaction with the site, increasing satisfaction and engagement.

- **General updates (based on the initial website structure):**
 - A newsletter section has been created to allow users who have not subscribed to the website to be informed of regular updates on the project, including news, events, and the latest developments. This tool is key to keeping the audience informed and engaged, facilitating ongoing communication, and providing a direct way to share the latest results and achievements.
- **Results section:** this section has been added in order to implement an effective dissemination strategy. The various public deliverables will be published here, as well as the promotional materials created for dissemination. This area allows both stakeholders and the general public to access the results in a clear way, ensuring transparency and fostering understanding of the impacts achieved.
- **New sections on the website:** During the last year, new sections have been added to the TWINNEDbySTARS website, with the aim of improving the visibility of the project, facilitating access to the results and strengthening the community that surrounds it.
 - On the one hand, the Our Community section has been created, which functions as a directory of the companies that are part of the TWINNEDbySTARS community. Companies have given their consent to appear in this section, which allows them to be filtered by region and good practices. This facilitates the identification of synergies between relevant actors in the sector and highlights the diversity and commitment of the entities involved.
 - On the other hand, within the Results section, a new subsection dedicated to co-creation has been added, where you can consult the methodology used in the workshops carried out, some statistics on the participants, infographics with detailed information on the tourism products co-created during the workshops, as well as audiovisual material that shows the key moments of these collaborative sessions.
 - Finally, also in the 'Results' section, within the framework of Task 2.2 (Development and application of training and self-diagnosis tools to identify opportunities for innovation), a specific section has been created on the website where all TWINNEDbySTARS online training courses are listed. To access this content, you must subscribe to the project newsletter, which keeps the community interested in capacity building informed and connected.
- **Google Analytics:** A Google Analytics tag has been inserted on the website to measure and analyse visits and user behaviour. This tag has been implemented under the Global Site Tag (gtag.js), using the identifiers G-50BCGK4WCX. This allows the collection of valuable data that facilitates website optimization, improving the user experience by analysing key metrics such as duration of visits, most viewed pages, and traffic sources.

- **Privacy and Compliance:** The Privacy and Compliance section has been created to ensure that the site complies with European and international data protection regulations. It is divided into two main parts:
- **Cookies Policy:** This section explains the use of cookies on the website, which are small text files stored on the user's device to improve their browsing experience. It describes the type of cookies used (technical, analytical, advertising, etc.), the purpose of each one, and how users can manage their cookie preferences. It ensures that users can accept or reject the use of cookies as they see fit, in compliance with the relevant regulations.
- **GDPR Compliance:** This part addresses compliance with the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which regulates the processing of users' personal data. The section details users' rights, including the right to access, rectify, or delete their personal data, as well as to limit or object to the processing of their personal data. It also explains the security measures adopted to protect users' personal information and how users can contact the team responsible for exercising their rights. In this way, secure and transparent browsing is guaranteed, ensuring that the website is fully aligned with current privacy and data protection regulations.

WEBSITE INSIGHTS

The following insights show the overall data in terms of statistics and interactions with the project's website since its launch at the earliest stage (M3) of the project:

Figure 12. Website insights.

TWINNEDbySTARS has achieved within the first two years of the project a total of **3.500 visits** and approximately **11.000 page interactions**.

Analysis of the top 10 countries with the most visitors reveals that TWINNEDbySTARS has been predominantly visited by Spanish and Portuguese audiences since the launch of the website, followed by Germany and Martinique.

Country		Active users	New users
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Total	779 100% of total	775 100% of total
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 Spain	411 (52.76%)	410 (52.9%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 Portugal	171 (21.95%)	169 (21.81%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 Germany	26 (3.34%)	25 (3.23%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 Martinique	25 (3.21%)	25 (3.23%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	5 France	17 (2.18%)	16 (2.06%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	6 Netherlands	14 (1.8%)	12 (1.55%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	7 United Kingdom	14 (1.8%)	14 (1.81%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	8 Belgium	13 (1.67%)	12 (1.55%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	9 United States	10 (1.28%)	10 (1.29%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	10 China	9 (1.16%)	9 (1.16%)

Figure 13. Ranking of the most visited countries on the unique users.

WEBSITE ARTICLES

Since M3 to M24 of the TWINNEDbySTARS project, a total of **59 articles** were published on the project’s website. These articles play a crucial role in informing and engaging the target audience, providing insights into the project's progress, key achievements, related industry news, and collaborative efforts. By systematically sharing detailed updates and reports, transparency can be ensured, and a deeper understanding of the work can be fostered among stakeholders, partners, and the wider community. It is vital to maintain interest and encourage participation.

Date	Title	Link
13/10/2023	European Union Unveils Groundbreaking Initiatives for Sustainable Maritime Development	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2023/10/13/european-union-unveils-groundbreaking-initiatives-for-sustainable-maritime-development/
27/10/2023	Gran Canaria Hosts TWINNEDbySTARS Project, Pioneering Maritime Ecotourism Initiative	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2023/10/27/gran-canaria-hosts-twinnedbystars-project-pioneering-maritime-ecotourism-initiative/
02/11/2023	TWINNEDbySTARS Business Meeting – “EXPERIENCES AT SEA... PEOPLE THAT INSPIRE”	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2023/11/02/twinned-by-stars-business-meeting-experiences-at-sea-people-that-inspire/
14/12/2023	Canary Islands Shine as Host of the Ultraperipheral Regions Conference.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2023/12/14/canary-islands-shine-as-host-of-the-ultraperipheral-regions-conference/
26/12/2023	The Government of the Canary Islands presented the findings of the 2023 Report of the Observatory of Sustainable Tourism.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2023/12/26/the-government-of-the-canary-islands-presented-the-findings-of-the-2023-report-of-the-observatory-of-sustainable-tourism/
19/01/2024	Dive into Watersport Innovation with EBI at Boot Düsseldorf 2024!	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/01/19/dive-into-watersport-innovation-with-ebi-at-boot-dusseldorf-2024/
24/01/2024	Unlocking Innovation in the Blue Economy with the ‘EU Blue Champions’ Scheme	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/01/24/unlocking-innovation-in-the-blue-economy-with-the-eu-blue-champions-scheme/
31/01/2024	EU main achievements in 2023 in tourism	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/01/31/eu-main-achievements-in-2023-in-tourism/
01/02/2024	Venture Capital Investors Explore New Horizons in Sustainable Marine Transport	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/02/01/venture-capital-investors-explore-new-horizons-in-sustainable-marine-transport/
07/02/2024	Join the TWINNEDbySTARS Network	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/02/07/join-the-twinnedbystars-network/
20/02/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS at B-Travel 2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/02/20/twinned-by-stars-at-b-travel-2024/
23/02/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS Joins Prestigious Lineup at European Ocean Days 2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/02/23/twinnedby-stars-joins-prestigious-lineup-at-european-ocean-days-2024/
15/03/2024	Discovering the ocean at European Oceans Days	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/03/15/discovering-the-ocean-at-european-oceans-days/

20/03/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS Presented at the B-Travel Event in Barcelona by Nautic Oceans Partners	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/03/20/twinnedby-stars-presented-at-the-b-travel-event-in-barcelona-by-nautic-oceans-partners/
01/04/2024	The Art of Sailing is presented by Nautic Oceans!	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/04/01/the-art-of-sailing-is-presented-by-nautic-oceans/
18/04/2024	Nautic Oceans unveils commemorative event for World Night: TWINNEDbySTARS presentation	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/04/18/nautic-oceans-unveils-commemorative-event-for-world-night-twinnedbystars-presentation/
02/05/2024	University Institute of Tourism and Sustainable Economic Development Tides is looking for research talent for TWINNEDbySTARS project	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/02/university-institute-of-tourism-and-sustainable-economic-development-tides-is-looking-for-research-talent-for-twinnedbystars-project/
06/05/2024	Discover the Secrets of the Universe at the 'Stellar Tour' Event!	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/06/discover-the-secrets-of-the-universe-at-the-stellar-tour-event/
15/05/2024	The decade of success of the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund in ocean conservation.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/15/the-decade-of-success-of-the-european-maritime-fisheries-and-aquaculture-fund-in-ocean-conservation/
21/05/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS Project joins European Maritime Day 2024 in Svendborg, Denmark	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/21/twinnedby-stars-project-joins-european-maritime-day-2024-in-svendborg-denmark/
22/05/2024	The Stellar Tour's event ends with success.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/22/the-stellar-tours-event-ends-with-success/
24/05/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS to participate in FIMAR 2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/24/twinnedby-stars-to-participate-in-fimar-2024/
31/05/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS Participates in the European Maritime Day 2024 in Svendborg, Denmark	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/31/twinnedby-stars-participates-in-the-european-maritime-day-2024-in-svendborg-denmark/
03/06/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS to Participate in 'Impulso Azul' on June 6th in Las Palmas	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/03/twinnedby-stars-to-participate-in-impulso-azul-on-june-6th-in-las-palmas/
04/06/2024	The Partners of Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique Presented TWINNEDbySTARS at the Martinique Boat Show, 4th Edition	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/04/the-partners-of-collectivite-territoriale-de-martinique-presented-twinnedbystars-at-the-martinique-boat-show-4th-edition/
11/06/2024	TWINNEDbySTAR Shines at FIMAR 2024: A Boost for the Blue Economy	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/11/twinnedby-star-shines-at-fimar-2024-a-boost-for-the-blue-economy/

19/06/2024	CTM presents TWINNEDbySTARS to SMEs in the Martinique Marine Sector	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/19/ctm-presents-twinnedbystars-to-smes-in-the-martinique-marine-sector/
21/06/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS Boosts Astrotourism with a Masterclass for SMEs in the Maritime Tourism Sector in the Canary Islands.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/21/twinnedby-stars-boosts-astrotourism-with-a-masterclass-for-smes-in-the-maritime-tourism-sector-in-the-canary-islands/
18/07/2024	Successful Completion of the Masterclass Sessions for SMEs in the Maritime Tourism Sector	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/07/18/successful-completion-of-the-masterclass-sessions-for-smes-in-the-maritime-tourism-sector/
21/08/2024	Invitation to co-creation sessions for SMEs of the maritime tourism sector in the Canary Islands, Madeira, Azores and Martinique	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/08/21/invitation-to-co-creation-sessions-for-smes-of-the-maritime-tourism-sector-in-the-canary-islands-madeira-azores-and-martinique/
10/09/2024	The 'TWINNEDbySTARS' Project at the Olympic Port during the America's Cup 2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/09/10/the-twinnedbystars-project-at-the-olympic-port-during-the-americas-cup-2024/
24/09/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS brings together experts and SMEs from the maritime tourism and nautical sector in Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/09/24/twinnedby-stars-brings-together-experts-and-smes-from-the-maritime-tourism-and-nautical-sector-in-las-palmas-de-gran-canaria/
22/10/2024	The first official TWINNEDbySTARS video is out!	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/10/22/the-first-official-twinnedbystars-video-is-out/
25/10/2024	Madeira hosts the second TWINNEDbySTARS' co-creation workshop	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/10/25/madeira-hosts-the-second-twinnedbystars-co-creation-workshop/
15/11/2024	Successful Co-creation Workshop in Martinique Drives Synergies in the TWINNEDbySTARS Community	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/11/15/successful-co-creation-workshop-in-martinique-drives-synergies-in-the-twinnedbystars-community/
22/11/2024	Cetecima participates in the Atlantic Week 2024 in Bordeaux	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/11/22/cetecima-participates-in-the-atlantic-week-2024-in-bordeaux/
29/11/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS held its project meeting and last co-creation workshop in Faial.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/11/29/twinnedby-stars-held-its-project-meeting-and-last-co-creation-workshop-in-faial/
13/12/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS Co-Creation Workshops: Innovation and Sustainability in Marine Tourism	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/12/13/twinnedby-stars-co-creation-workshops-innovation-and-sustainability-in-marine-tourism/
09/01/2025	TWINNEDbySTARS was presented during the presentation	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/01/09/twinnedby-stars-was-presented-during-the-presentation-of-the-book-diminuto-planeta-azul-tiny-blue-planet/

	of the book Diminuto Planeta Azul (Tiny Blue Planet)	
15/01/2025	Now available: Self-Assessment Tool for Companies in the Maritime Sector	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/01/15/boosting-sustainable-and-digital-tourism-in-the-outermost-regions/
27/01/2025	TWINNEDbySTARS: Key Results Transforming Tourism in the Outermost Regions	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/01/27/twinnedby-stars-key-results-transforming-tourism-in-the-outermost-regions/
29/01/2025	TWINNEDbySTARS strengthens its impact by participating in the kick-off meeting of the A3MAtlantic project.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/01/29/twinnedby-stars-strengthens-its-impact-by-participating-in-the-kick-off-meeting-of-the-a3matlantic-project/
31/01/2025	Discover the new sections of our website!	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/01/31/discover-the-new-sections-of-our-website/
21/02/2025	TWINNEDbySTARS launches two free courses on artificial intelligence for the nautical sector	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/02/21/twinnedby-stars-launches-two-free-courses-on-artificial-intelligence-for-the-nautical-sector/
10/03/2025	KEEP SAILING, the first nautical company in the Canary Islands certified as Starlight 2025	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/03/10/keep-sailing-the-first-nautical-company-in-the-canary-islands-certified-as-starlight-2025/
17/03/2025	TWINNEDbySTARS: Espejo Canario Interview with Keep Sailing, the First Canarian Nautical Company with Starlight Certification	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/03/17/twinnedby-stars-espejo-canario-interview-with-keep-sailing-the-first-canarian-nautical-company-with-starlight-certification/
21/03/2025	Keep Sailing is crowned under the stars: Gran Canaria celebrates the first Starlight-certified nautical astronomical observation	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/03/21/keep-sailing-is-crowned-under-the-stars-gran-canaria-celebrates-the-first-starlight-certified-nautical-astronomical-observation/
14/04/2025	Registration is now open for the SEA STARLIGHT Monitor training course for nautical companies interested in astro-tourism.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/04/14/registration-is-now-open-for-the-sea-starlight-monitor-training-course-for-nautical-companies-interested-in-astro-tourism/
22/04/2025	Madeira Sunkiss Sailing, the first maritime company in Portugal to obtain Starlight certification thanks to TWINNEDbySTARS	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/04/22/madeira-sunkiss-sailing-the-first-maritime-company-in-portugal-to-obtain-starlight-certification-thanks-to-twinnedbystars/
07/05/2025	TWINNEDbySTARS contributes to the European debate on the future of sustainable maritime tourism in the Outermost Regions in the EMDs	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/05/07/twinnedby-stars-contributes-to-the-european-debate-on-the-future-of-sustainable-maritime-tourism-in-the-outermost-regions-in-the-emds/

27/05/2025	TWINNEDbySTARS boosts the debate on maritime and coastal tourism in the Outermost Regions at the European Maritime Day in Cork	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/05/27/twinnedbystars-boosts-the-debate-on-maritime-and-coastal-tourism-in-the-outermost-regions-at-the-european-maritime-day-in-cork/
03/06/2025	The TWINNEDbySTARS project, protagonist of the next episode of OCEAN on Euronews	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/06/03/the-twinnedbystars-project-protagonist-of-the-next-episode-of-ocean-on-euronews/
17/06/2025	The practical phase of the Marine Starguide certification takes place in Azores and Madeira	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/06/17/the-practical-phase-of-the-marine-starguide-certification-takes-place-in-azores-and-madeira/
25/07/2025	TWINNEDbySTARS launches its first products in the Atlantic: on-board training and nautical experiences under the stars	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/06/25/twinnedbystars-launches-its-first-products-in-the-atlantic-on-board-training-and-nautical-experiences-under-the-stars/
03/07/2025	Researchers warn about the risks of poorly managed whale watching tourism in the Canary Islands, Madeira and the Azores	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/07/03/researchers-warn-about-the-risks-of-poorly-managed-whale-watching-tourism-in-the-canary-islands-madeira-and-the-azores/
30/07/2025	TWINNEDbySTARS stars in the new episode of Euronews' OCEAN documentary series	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/07/30/twinnedbystars-stars-in-the-new-episode-of-euronews-ocean-documentary-series/

Table 5. List of TWINNEDbySTARS's website articles.

The table below lists the **44 articles that have been published on the project partners' websites so far**. Each entry includes the article title, publication date, and a link to the full text. These articles showcase the collaborative achievements, innovations, and progress made under the project.

Date	Partner	Title	Link
24/10/2023	FPCT-ULPGC	Europa impulsa el turismo marino sostenible en sus territorios ultraperiféricos con el proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/es/noticias/item/817-europa-impulsa-el-turismo-marino-sostenible-en-sus-territorios-ultraperifericos-con-el-proyecto-twinnedbystars.html
26/10/2023		El Parque Científico Tecnológico escenario de la presentación del proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS, una iniciativa pionera de ecoturismo marítimo	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/es/noticias/item/820-el-parque-cientifico-tecnologico-escenario-de-la-presentacion-del-proyecto-twinnedbystars-una-iniciativa-pionera-de-ecoturismo-maritimo.html
13/05/2024		Descubre los secretos del universo en el evento "Stelar Tour: Mythology,	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/es/noticias/item/909-descubre-los-secretos-del-universo-en-el-evento-stelar-tour

		Starlight and Navigation Curiosities”, organizado por la ULPGC como parte del evento European Maritime Day in My Country, 16 de mayo de 2024	mythology-starlight-and-navigation-curiosities-organizado-por-la-ulpgccomo-parte-del-evento-european-maritime-day-in-my-country-16-de-mayo-de-2024.html
24/09/2024		TWINNEDbySTARS reúne a expertos y PYME del turismo marítimo y la náutica en Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/en/noticias/it-em/985-twinnedbystars-reune-a-expertos-y-pyme-del-turismo-maritimo-y-la-nautica-en-las-palmas-de-gran-canaria.html
26/03/2025		Proyecto TWINNEDBySTARS y Keep Sailing se coronan bajo las estrellas: Gran Canaria celebra la primera observación astronómica náutica con certificación Starlight	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/es/noticias/it-em/1224-evento-de-observacion-astronomica-en-gran-canaria.html
15/04/2024		Los navegantes demandan marinas sostenibles	https://theconversation.com/los-navegantes-demandan-marinas-sostenibles-225826
23/10/2023		TWINNEDBySTARS, un proyecto liderado en Canarias, para fomentar el turismo náutico regenerativo	https://tides.ulpgc.es/twinnedbystars-un-proyecto-liderado-en-canarias-para-fomentar-el-turismo-nautico-regenerativo/
29/04/2024	TIDES-ULPGC	La sostenibilidad en la navegación recreativa, examinada por tres investigadores de la ULPGC en The Conversation	https://www.ulpgc.es/noticia/2024/04/29/sostenibilidad-navegacion-recreativa-examinada-tres-investigadores-ulpgc
19/09/2024		Evento de co-creación reúne a expertos y PYMEs del turismo marítimo y la náutica en Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/es/noticias/it-em/983-evento-de-co-creacion-reune-a-expertos-y-pymes-del-turismo-maritimo-y-la-nautica-en-las-palmas-de-gran-canaria.html
28/02/2025		Proyecto TBS: Obtén nuestro apoyo para certificarte como empresa Starlight	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/es/noticias/it-em/1043-proyecto-twinnedbystars-obten-nuestro-apoyo-para-certificarte-como-empresa-starlight.html

12/03/2025		El Instituto Tides promueve la primera Empresa Náutica Starlight certificada en Canarias	https://tides.ulpgc.es/el-instituto-tides-promueve-la-primera-empresa-nautica-starlight-certificada-en-canarias/
17/03/2025		La ULPGC impulsa la navegación astronómica como estrategia de diversificación del turismo	https://www.ulpgc.es/noticia/2025/03/17/ulpgc-impulsa-navegacion-astronomica-como-estrategia-diversificacion-del-turismo
31/10/2023	CE	Launch of the TWINNEDbySTARS Project: Transforming Europe's Outermost Regions into International Maritime Ecotourism Destinations	https://consulta-europa.com/lanzamiento-del-proyecto-twinnedbystars-transformando-las-regiones-ultraperifericas-europeas-en-destinos-internacionales-de-ecoturismo-maritimo/
19/02/2024		Join the TWINNEDbySTARS Project	https://consulta-europa.com/unete-al-proyecto-twinnedbystars/
08/05/2024		TWINNEDbySTARS Invites to the 'Stellar Tour' Event: Discover the Secrets of the Universe!	https://consulta-europa.com/consulta-europa-invites-to-the-stellar-tour-event-discover-the-secrets-of-the-universe/
21/08/2024		We invite you to participate in the co-creation workshops of the TWINNEDbySTARS project.	https://consulta-europa.com/we-invite-you-to-participate-in-the-co-creation-workshops-of-the-twinnedbystars-project/
05/12/2024		TWINNEDbySTARS held its project meeting and last co-creation workshop in Faial	https://consulta-europa.com/twinnedbystars-held-its-project-meeting-and-last-co-creation-workshop-in-faial/
31/01/2025		TWINNEDbySTARS: Key Results Transforming Tourism in the Outermost Regions	https://consulta-europa.com/twinnedbystars-key-results-transforming-tourism-in-the-outermost-regions/
01/08/2025		TWINNEDbySTARS stars in the new episode of Euronews' OCEAN documentary series	https://consulta-europa.com/twinnedbystars-stars-in-the-new-episode-of-euronews-ocean-documentary-series/
30/06/2025		TWINNEDbySTARS launches its first products in the Atlantic: on-board training and nautical	https://consulta-europa.com/twinnedbystars-launches-its-first-products-in-the-atlantic-on-

		experiences under the stars	board-training-and-nautical-experiences-under-the-stars/
19/10/2023	CMC	TWINNEDBySTARS, un proyecto liderado en Canarias, para fomentar el turismo náutico regenerativo	https://www.clustermc.es/twinnedbystars-un-proyecto-liderado-en-canarias-para-fomentar-el-turismo-nautico-regenerativo/
08/02/2024		Descubre el proyecto europeo TWINNEDbySTARS	https://www.clustermc.es/descubre-el-proyecto-europeo-twinnedbystars/
03/06/2024		El CMC participa en el European Maritime Day de Svendborg, Dinamarca	https://www.clustermc.es/el-cmc-involucrado-en-el-european-maritime-day/
06/06/2024		Las Palmas de Gran Canaria y Viana do Castelo Impulsan la Economía Azul	https://www.clustermc.es/las-palmas-de-gran-canaria-y-viana-do-castelo-impulsan-la-economia-azul/
10/06/2024		CMC, FEDEPORT y el IFPMP Fomentan las Vocaciones Azules en FIMAR 2024	https://www.clustermc.es/cmc-fedeport-y-el-ifpmp-fomentan-las-vocaciones-azules-en-fimar-2024/
24/09/2024		El CMC fomenta la certificación del turismo náutico en el proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS	https://www.clustermc.es/el-cmc-fomenta-la-certificacion-del-turismo-nautico-en-el-proyecto-twinnedbystars/
25/10/2024		Taller de Co-creación en Madeira – TwinnedbyStars	https://clustermc.es/taller-de-co-creacion-en-madeira-twinnedbystars/
15/11/2024		Taller Co-creación TWINNEDbySTARS en Martinica	https://clustermc.es/taller-co-creacion-twinnedbystars-en-martinica/
29/11/2024		TWINNEDbySTARS celebró su reunión de proyecto y el último taller de cocreación en Faial.	https://clustermc.es/twinnedbystars-celebro-su-reunion-de-proyecto-y-el-ultimo-taller-de-cocreacion-en-faial/
12/03/2025		Keep Sailing, primera empresa náutica certificada Starlight 2025 en el proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS	https://clustermc.es/keep-sailing-primera-empresa-nautica-certificada-starlight-2025-en-el-proyecto-twinnedbystars/
15/04/2025		Formación de monitores Sea Starlight del proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS	https://clustermc.es/formacion-de-monitores-sea-starlight-deel-proyecto-twinnedbystars/
26/05/2025		AquaWind lleva la innovación azul de Canarias a las jornadas del	https://clustermc.es/aquawind-lleva-la-innovacion-azul-de-canarias-a-las-jornadas-de-conmemoracion-del-dia-maritimo-europeo-2025-en-cork/

		Día Marítimo Europeo 2025 en Cork	
28/03/2024	Nautic Ocean	El turismo náutico en la Regiones Ultraperiféricas de la UE	https://www.nauticocean.com/blog/el-turismo-nautico-en-la-regiones-ultraperifericas-de-la-ue/
20/11/2023	CETECIMA	Kick off meeting article	https://www.cetecima.com/?p=4107
02/08/2024		CETECIMA aporta su 'know-how' para un turismo náutico sostenible en Canarias a través del proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS	https://www.cetecima.com/cetecima-aporta-su-know-how-para-un-turismo-nautico-sostenible-en-canarias-a-traves-del-proyecto-twinnedbystars/
08/11/2023	MARINA FUNCHAL	Marina do Funchal presente no lançamento do projeto TWINNEDbyStars	https://www.marinadofunchal.pt/islandmadeira/marina-do-funchal-presente-no-lancamento-do-projeto-twinnedbystars/
30/10/2023	ACIF-CCIM	ACIF marca presença na primeira reunião de lançamento do projeto TWINNEDbySTARS	https://www.acif-ccim.pt/2023/10/30/acif-marca-presenca-na-primeira-reuniao-de-lancamento-projeto-twinnedbystars/?doing_wp_cron=1723371394.6771159172058105468750
10/10/2024		Convite – Workshop de Cocriação a 23-24 de outubro	Convite - Workshop de Cocriação a 23-24 de outubro - ACIF-CCIM
24/10/2024		MADEIRA ACOLHEU O SEGUNDO WORKSHOP DE COCRIAÇÃO DO TWINNEDBYSTARS	https://www.acif-ccim.pt/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/20241024_madeira_acolheu_tbs.pdf
11/04/2025		Formação - Monitor Sea Starlight. Não perca a oportunidade! Lugares limitados	https://mkt.acif-ccim.pt/vl/c-34-b10ec9b8f06a6da6-58774103cb8341d5cfbe2aJe1Qyffe1ozFe9-40-3510c?utm_source=e-goi&utm_medium=email&utm_term=Forma%C3%A7%C3%A3o+-+Monitor+Sea+Starlight.+N%C3%A3o+perca+a+oportunidade%21+Lugares+limitados&utm_campaign=Colaboradores+ACIF
17/06/2025		ACIF-CCIM - Apresentação produto marítimo-Turístico	https://www.acif-ccim.pt/2025/06/17/apresentacao-do-produto-maritimo-turistico/
16/11/2023	EBI	Presentation at EBI Council EBI Council Internal meeting INTERNAL	Microsoft PowerPoint - EBI Council - 16112023 - Full presentation (europeanboatingindustry.eu)

30/11/2024		EBI joins EU-funded TWINNEDbySTARS, Pioneering Maritime Ecotourism	https://www.europeanboatingindustry.eu/newsroom/newsletter/item/872-ebi-joins-eu-funded-twinnedbystars-pioneering-maritime-ecotourism
23/04/2024		Presentation at EBI Council EBI Council Internal meeting INTERNAL	Microsoft PowerPoint - EBI Council Meeting April Project Update 1 (europeanboatingindustry.eu)

Table 6. List of TWINNEDbySTARS articles published on project partners' websites.

It is worth noting that the project has been mentioned on the websites of the European Commission-CINEA.

Date	Title	Link
Unknown	Project TWINNEDbySTARS	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/featured-projects/twinnedbystars_en
22/02/2024	Where next for Europe's Seas: the contribution of EU-funded projects at EU Ocean Days	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/eu-projects-sustainable-blue-economy-eu-ocean-days-2024-02-22_en
12/10/2023	New EMFAF Regional flagship projects just kicked off their work!	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/new-emfaf-regional-flagship-projects-just-kicked-their-work-2023-10-12_en
30/05/2024	European Maritimes Day 2024	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/events/european-maritime-day-2024-2024-05-30_en
Unknown	Projects at EMD 2024 EU Stand	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/document/download/05c4ad20-4a06-46d5-8aa2-8e9454067386_en?filename=list-of-projects-EMD2024_Final.pdf
01/10/2024	2024 EMD In My Country - local events	https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/document/download/3bbc44f8-bab4-4e48-b5da-3ccb710781d6_en?filename=european-maritime-day-events-in-europe-2024-per-country_en_0.pdf
01/10/2024	2024 EMD In My Country - Overview of local events	https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/document/download/e6b802f2-f5b2-45a6-b01f-f6b3ed804a96_en?filename=EMD%20IMC%202024%20events%20By%20Country%20updated%2022.5.pdf
Unknown	2024 EMD In My Country events per date - 2024	https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/document/download/576b5833-85a7-42c5-819d-0f46296c0962_en?filename=european-

	maritime-day-events-in-europe-2024-per-date_en.pdf
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Table 7. TWINNEDbySTARS articles published on CINEA website.

4.4 Newsletter

To effectively communicate the latest updates and achievements of the TWINNEDbySTARS project, WP5 utilizes a dynamic newsletter as a key outreach tool. Newsletters are an invaluable resource for keeping stakeholders informed and engaged, offering a regular stream of updates on project milestones, new developments, and key achievements.

The inaugural edition was distributed on February 23, 2024, reaching a network of 108 recipients and published on the project’s website to boost its outreach to new visitors. This newsletter not only highlights the D&C progress but also plays a pivotal role in fostering interest and involvement among stakeholders.

The final structure established for the first newsletter, launched in M5, included a series of sections designed to introduce and raise awareness of the project. It began with an introduction entitled Introducing TWINNEDbySTARS, followed by Meet TWINNEDbySTARS, where the project was introduced in more detail. The main objectives of the project were also addressed, along with a detailed explanation of who we are and what we do. In addition, readers were invited to become part of our community. A section dedicated to the latest news was included, as well as a part on related projects, also known as sister projects. Finally, readers were informed about upcoming events and next steps of the project.

Figure 14. First newsletter release

On 26 September 2024, the second newsletter, designed to provide recent project updates from M5 to M12, was published on the TWINNEDbySTARS website. In this edition, WP5 has added the premiere of the project’s first official video, as well as including recent updates and activities. This update keeps subscribers abreast of the latest developments and maintains commitment to the ongoing development of the project. A community of 237 subscribers received the second newsletter.

New Constellations Formed: Tracing Brilliant Connections between the Outermost Regions

Figure 15. Second newsletter release.

On 25 February 2025, the third TWINNEDbySTARS newsletter was published on the TWINNEDbySTARS website, with news from M13 to M17 of the project. This edition presented the new animated video of the project, the latest updates of the website and the launch of the Self-Assessment Tool. It also shared the results of the voting of the tourism products, a new training activity under the title Boost Your Digital Strategy with Free AI Training, the most recent events and synergies established, as well as the next steps planned. This newsletter was sent to a community of 275 subscribers interested in following the progress of the project. Figure 17. third newsletter release.

A new horizon for TWINNEDbySTARS

Figure 16. Third newsletter release.

On 26 September 2025, the fourth TWINNEDbySTARS newsletter was distributed, covering the latest developments and activities of the project. This edition presented the launch of the first collaborative products in the outermost regions, including certified training practices on board and the Atlantic Starlight Adventures platform for nautical experiences under the stars. It also highlighted the Starlight 2025 certifications obtained by Keep Sailing in the Canary Islands and Madeira Sunkiss Sailing in Madeira, reinforcing the role of astronomy in sustainable tourism.

In addition, the newsletter included the results of recent training activities, such as the practical phase of the Marine Starguide course in the Azores and Madeira, as well as scientific publications

on responsible whale watching in the Canary Islands, Madeira and the Azores. Finally, the next steps in product testing, marketing and business plan development were presented, underlining the project's commitment to innovative, sustainable and educational maritime tourism experiences.

Figure 17. Fourth newsletter release

The newsletters are available at: <https://twinnedbystars.eu/newsletters/>.

Our newsletter currently has a total of **396 subscribers**. Of these, **383 remain active** and continue to receive our updates, while **13 have chosen to unsubscribe**. This reflects a high level of interest and engagement from our community.

Status	Total
Any	396
Confirmed	383
Not confirmed	0
Unsubscribed	13
Bounced	0
Complained	0

Figure 18. Subscribers for the newsletter.

Moreover, partners have also featured the project in their own institutional newsletters, with a total of 12 articles published across their bulletins.

Date	Partner	Title	Link
19/10/2024	CMC	“Experiences at sea: people that inspire”: business meeting with nautical and maritime entrepreneurs	https://mailchi.mp/clustermc/noticias-de-inters-17073632
14/02/2024		“Discover a word inspired by stars and the ocean”	https://mailchi.mp/clustermc/noticias-de-inters-17633444?e=b37857c7ff
13/05/2024		“Experiences at sea: people that inspire”: business meeting with nautical and maritime entrepreneurs	https://mailchi.mp/clustermc/noticias-de-inters-17073632
26/02/2025		FORMACIÓN - TWINNEDbySTARS	https://clustermc.es/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/FORMACION-TwinnedbyStars.pdf
17/02/2025		Vota ahora para elegir la mejor idea de negocio de TWINNEDbySTARS	https://clustermc.es/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/Vota-ahora-para-elegir-la-mejor-idea-de-negocio-de-TWINNEDbySTARS.pdf
24/01/2025		Impulsa el turismo sostenible TWINNEDbySTARS	https://clustermc.es/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/TwinnedbyStars-cuestionario-para-impulsar-el-turismo-sostenible.pdf
18/09/2024		Taller de co-creación proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS	https://clustermc.es/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/Programa-de-Aceleracion-IAT-Taller-Proyecto-TwinnedbyStars.pdf
31/12/2023	TIDES-ULPGC	Newsletter Diciembre 2023	https://tides.ulpgc.es/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Newsletter-Diciembre-23.pdf
31/12/2023	ACIF-ACCIM	Newsletter Dezembro 2023	https://mkt.acif-ccim.pt/vl/80053fa1e1260d2a7fa913ad58937331fdafd97fae1G9e1LLjfe1ozFe9-40-3510c
Unknown		Feiras Internacionais	Feiras internacionais (acif-ccim.pt)
Unknown		Conferência do Setor Náutico 2024	Conferência do Setor Náutico 2024 (acif-ccim.pt)
Unknown		Aconteceu em junho	https://mkt.acif-ccim.pt/vl/82f2c67ce0ba41--cd00373d009c6fddf48631876e2hue1Rnu2e1ozFe9-40-3510c?utm_source=e-

			goi&utm_medium=email&utm_term=A CIF-CCIM+- +Aconteceu+em+junho+de+2025&utm _campaign=Colaboradores+ACIF
30/10/2023	EBI	EBI joins EU-funded TWINNEDbySTARS, Pioneering Maritime Ecotourism	EBI joins EU-funded TWINNEDbySTARS, Pioneering Maritime Ecotourism (europeanboatingindustry.eu)

Table 8. List of TWINNEDbySTARS articles published on project partners' newsletters.

4.5 Social Media

In accordance with the Grant Agreement, WP5 has established a presence on several social media platforms to reach a broader audience. The primary channels—X, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Facebook—allow connecting with a diverse range of target groups, including SMEs, policymakers, decision-makers, other stakeholders, and other EU projects and initiatives.

These accounts are regularly updated with valuable content such as project updates, news, digital campaigns, events, webinars, and other relevant activities. Their main purposes are:

- **Communication:** Facilitating real-time interaction and dialogue with the audience.
- **Information Sharing:** disseminating details about events, project activities, and sector news.
- **Community Engagement:** Building and nurturing a community around the project.
- **Promotion:** Highlighting project actions and achievements.
- **Networking:** connecting professionals and organizations, fostering collaboration, and creating opportunities for growth (including collaboration with sister projects).
- **Education and Awareness:** Raising awareness about the marine environment, blue and circular economies, and sustainable practices in ecotourism.

The following table shows a general view about the performance on each channel from October 2023 (M1) until September 2025 (M24):

Social media	Link	N° posts	Followers
	TWINNEDbySTARS https://www.linkedin.com/company/twinned-by-stars/posts/?feedView=all	124	383
	@twinnedbystars https://www.instagram.com/twinnedbystars/	124	495
	Twinned by Stars https://www.facebook.com/twinnedbystars	123	75

	<p>@TwinnedbyStars https://twitter.com/TwinnedbyStars</p>	<p>156</p>	<p>112</p>
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Table 9. Social media channels.

All social media campaigns are typically supported by a well-planned strategy, in line with the overall D&C plan of the project, that includes an event announcement post, engaging content or curiosities to build anticipation, and a reminder post as the event approaches.

In the second year of the project, work will be done to increase the numbers on social media. Strategies will be implemented to increase reach and engagement across all platforms, improving the visibility of the project.

4.5.1 SOCIAL MEDIA INSIGHT

- **LinkedIn**

The presence on LinkedIn has generated significant engagement, reflecting the growing interest in the TWINNEDbySTARS project. In the last 24 months, **20.316 impressions** have been reached, indicating the level of visibility the content has gained among industry professionals and stakeholders. These impressions highlight the effectiveness of the outreach efforts made and the relevance of the updates, which include project milestones, event announcements, and industry insights. In the future, LinkedIn will continue to be leveraged to expand outreach, foster connections, and raise awareness of key initiatives undertaken.

The presence on LinkedIn has generated a remarkable level of interaction, reflecting the growing interest in the TWINNEDbySTARS project. During the first year, **18.869 impressions** were reached, evidencing the visibility gained among industry professionals and stakeholders. These impressions reflect the effectiveness of the dissemination efforts and the relevance of the publications, which have included project milestones, event announcements and industry-related content. Between M13 and M24, an additional **17.160 impressions** were added, consolidating LinkedIn as a key tool to extend reach, foster connections and give visibility to the project's initiatives.

Figure 19. Content performance. (M1 – 12)

Figure 20. Content performance. (M13-24)

• Facebook

Facebook activity has successfully captured the attention of a diverse audience, reflecting the widespread interest in the TWINNEDbySTARS project. During the first 24 months of the project, TWINNEDbySTARS posts have generated **29.101 reaches**, showcasing the content’s reach and engagement across the platform.

Figure 21. Facebook Growth.

• Instagram

The Instagram presence has been instrumental in visually engaging with the project’s audience and promoting the TWINNEDbySTARS project. The project has achieved **6.720 reaches**, highlighting the impact of its visually driven content on this platform. These impressions reflect the growing interest in the project’s updates, event highlights, and visual storytelling.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Figure 22. Instagram Growth.

- **Twitter/X**

During the first year of the project (M1–12), Twitter activity proved to be the most effective among the social media efforts, reaching **4,100 impressions** and demonstrating a strong impact in disseminating project news, updates, and sector-related content. These results highlight the effectiveness of the strategy in increasing visibility, fostering conversations, and connecting with key stakeholders and the broader community. In the second year (M13–24), Twitter continued to be a key channel, achieving **3,300 impressions**, which demonstrates its ongoing role in promoting the project and maintaining consistent reach among stakeholders.

Figure 23. Twitter Interactions. (M 1-12)

Figure 24. Twitter Interactions. (M 13-24)

4.6 Press releases

Press releases issued during the first year of the TWINNEDbySTARS project have been essential to disseminate the project's achievements and broader developments. These official releases have been strategically created to keep the media and the stakeholders informed of the project's progress.

This section includes a list of the **32 actions of earn media** that have been distributed, of which **3 is international (2 Online press, 1 TV)**, **3 are national (1 online press, 2 radio)** and **26 are regional (1 Journal, 16 online press, 5 radio & 4 TV)**, each highlighting the importance of their contribution to the promotion and dissemination of the project.

Date	Title	Media	Type of media	Dissemination level	Link
Project launch & kick off meeting					
12/10/2023	New EMFAF Regional flagship projects just kicked off their work!	CINEA	Online press	INTERNATIONAL	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/new-emfaf-regional-flagship-projects-just-kicked-their-work-2023-10-12_en
18/10/2023	Twinnedbystars, un proyecto liderado en Canarias, para fomentar el	El Espejo Canario	Radio	REGIONAL	https://www.elespejocanario.es/secciones/twinnedbystars-un-proyecto-liderado-en-canarias-

	turismo náutico regenerativo				para-fomentar-el-turismo-nautico-regenerativo/
27/10/2023	Gran Canaria organiza o proyecto "TWINNEDbySTARS"	Dnoticias	Online press	REGIONAL	Gran Canaria organiza o proyecto 'TWINNEDbySTARS' — DNOTICIAS.PT
01/10/2023	Madeira integra projeto europeu para a biodiversidade marinha e combate às alterações climáticas	O jornal económico	Online press	NATIONAL	https://jornaleconomico.sapo.pt/noticias/madeira-integra-projeto-europeu-para-a-biodiversidade-marinha-e-combate-as-alteracoes-climaticas/
12/07/2024	CETECIMA aporta su 'know-how' para un turismo náutico sostenible en Canarias a través del proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS	Puertocanarias	Online press	REGIONAL	https://puertocanarias.com/es/node/7520
Stakeholder engagement campaign and other project dissemination actions					
30/11/2023	Analizamos el estado de la acuicultura	RTVE audio Españoles en la mar	Radio	NATIONAL	https://www.rtve.es/play/audios/espanoles-en-la-mar/analizamos-estado-acuicultura/7025191/
05/06/2024	Canarias participa en el Día Marítimo Europeo	El Espejo Canario	Radio	REGIONAL	Canarias participa en el Día Marítimo Europeo (elespejocanario.es)
06/06/2024	El encuentro 'Impulso Azul' anticipa FIMAR 2024	RTVC Radio TV Canaria	Radio	REGIONAL	https://rtvc.es/el-encuentro-impulso-azul-anticipa-fimar-2024/
06/06/2024	El impulso de la economía azul en el entorno atlántico, un esfuerzo conjunto entre Las Palmas de Gran Canaria y Viana do Castelo	Infopuertos	Online press	REGIONAL	https://infopuertos.com/lp-gc-viana-do-castelo-impulso-economia-azul/

06/06/2024	El encuentro 'Impulso Azul' anticipa FIMAR 2024	Televisión Canaria Informativo	TV	REGIONAL	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5OFsi7HfpSA
27/01/2024	Projeto TwinnedbySTARS lançado em Canárias	JM	Online press	REGIONAL	https://www.jm-madeira.pt/economia/ver/221729/Projeto_TWINNE_DbySTARS_lancado_em_Canarias
Co-creation workshops					
23/10/2024	Workshop TWINNEDBySTARS na Madeira	RTP	TV (Part 2 Minute 8:04)	REGIONAL	https://www.rtp.pt/play/p85/e803692/telejornal-madeira/1279369
24/10/2024	Madeira acolhe segundo workshop de cocriação do TwinnedByStars	JM	Online press	REGIONAL	Madeira acolhe o segundo workshop de cocriação do TWINNEDbySTARS
25/10/2024	Madeira acolhe segundo workshop de cocriação do TwinnedByStars	JM	Online Press	REGIONAL	https://www.jm-madeira.pt/regiao/madeira-palco-do-segundo-workshop-de-cocriacao-do-projeto-twinnedbystars-PL16953972
25/10/2024	Madeira acolhe segundo workshop de cocriação do TwinnedByStars	DNoticias.pt	Online Press	REGIONAL	Madeira acolheu workshop do projecto 'TwinnedByStars' que reuniu ainda Canárias, Açores e Martinica — DNOTICIAS.PT
29/11/2024	Consórcio de promoção do turismo marítimo e costeiro nas RUP reuniu nos Açores	DNoticias.pt	Online Press	REGIONAL	Consórcio de promoção de turismo marítimo e costeiro nas regiões ultraperiféricas reuniu nos Açores — DNOTICIAS.PT
Starlight Certification 2025					
12/03/2025	Keep Sailing, primera empresa canaria certificada como Starlight	El Espejo Canario	Online press + Radio	REGIONAL	https://www.elespejocanario.es/secciones/keep-sailing-primera-empresa-canaria-certificada-como-starlight/
14/03/2025	Keep Sailing, primera empresa náutica certificada Starlight 2025	INFOPUERTOS	Online Press	REGIONAL	https://infopuertos.com/keep-sailing-certificada-starlight-2025/

	en el proyecto TWINNEDbyST ARS				
17/03/2025	La ULPGC impulsa el turismo sostenible a través de la navegación astronómica guiada	CANARIAS 7	Online Press	REGIONAL	https://www.canarias7.es/sociedad/educacion/ulpgc-impulsa-turismo-sostenible-traves-navegacion-astronomica-20250317142823-nt.html
21/03/2025	Gran Canaria cuenta con la primera embarcación turística certificada para la observación de estrellas	Turismo Gran Canaria	Online Press	REGIONAL	https://www.grancanaria.com/turismo/es/area-profesional/noticias/noticia/?tx_ttnews%5Btt_news%5D=5098&cHash=57613669193ca0f20932547eed48caa
21/03/2025	Canarias, un destino para navegar bajo las estrellas: Turismo, ciencia y tradición se unen en una experiencia náutica pionera	CADENA SER	Radio	REGIONAL	https://www.grancanaria.com/turismo/es/area-profesional/noticias/noticia/?tx_ttnews%5Btt_news%5D=5098&cHash=57613669193ca0f20932547eed48caa
21/03/2025	Gran Canaria estrena la primera embarcación turística certificada para la observación de estrellas	MSN	Online Press	REGIONAL	https://www.msn.com/es-es/noticias/internacional/gran-canaria-estrena-la-primera-embarcaci%C3%B3n-tur%C3%ADstica-certificada-para-la-observaci%C3%B3n-de-estrellas/ar-AA1BoR0e
21/03/2025	Gran Canaria estrena la primera embarcación turística certificada para la observación de estrellas	La Provincia	Online Press	REGIONAL	https://www.laprovincia.es/gran-canaria/2025/03/21/gran-canaria-estrena-primera-embarcacion-115552593.html
24/03/2025	Buenos días Canarias (watch from 2h14min 36s onwards)	RTVC Radio TV Canaria	TV	REGIONAL	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PZ6KBgBLsJU&list=PLHagRXzKHn2NKs99qdeB_jTnmdcgSLkhg
25/03/2025	Gran Canaria cuenta con la primera	TOURINE WS	Online Press	REGIONAL	https://www.tourinews.es/destinos-turismo/gran-canaria-primera-

	embarcación turística certificada para la observación de estrellas				embarcacion-turistica-certificada-observacion-estrellas 4485910 102.html
06/04/2025	(from Minute 10.50) Nuevos estudios, laboratorios y proyectos de investigación	RTVE – Informativo ARU	Radio	NATIONAL	https://www.rtve.es/play/audios/informativo-aru-en-radio-exterior-de-espana/informativo-aru-nuevos-estudios-laboratorios-proyectos-investigacion/16517850/
17/06/2025	Astro turismo marinho arranca na region	JM Madeira	Journal	REGIONAL	N/A (physical print edition only)
22/06/2025	Observar os astros a partir do mar (vídeo)	RTP Madeira	TV	REGIONAL	https://madeira.rtp.pt/economia/observar-os-astros-a-partir-do-mar-video/?fbclid=IwY2xjawL_GWMBleHRuA2FibQIxMQBicmlkETB3Ym1zZ2hC RENPU1VzQTdzAR5HQ3lLZ9zvpwSgsB6OudSwjBYJO3VVR8vSKAaKEKx2BzNkbc1iIow2SJvxTw_aem_GMMY8XL8xgW2sjnKXO2oQ
Euronews documentary					
29/07/2025	How Atlantic islands are proving tourism can help the ocean	EURONEWS	Online Press and TV	INTERNATIONAL	https://www.euronews.com/green/2025/07/29/how-atlantic-islands-are-proving-tourism-can-help-the-ocean

Table 10. Press release list.

Throughout the project, **3 scientific publications** have been presented. These publications reflect the progress and findings obtained in the different areas of work of the project, providing rigorous evidence and analysis that support the activities carried out and the strategies implemented. The inclusion of these articles demonstrates the academic and technical impact of the project, as well as its contribution to knowledge in the field of tourism innovation and nautical experiences linked to the night sky.

Date	Title	Authors	Title of the journal	Link
June 2024	A scientometrics review of fifty years of whale-	Chaitanya Suárez-Rojas, Carmelo J.	Marine Policy	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2025.106658

	watching tourism research	León		
August 2024	Avistamiento de ballenas y delfines: lo bueno, lo malo y lo peligroso	Yen E. Lam González Chaitanya Suárez Rojas Juan Carlos Martín	The Conversation	https://theconversation.com/avistamiento-de-ballenas-y-delfines-lo-bueno-lo-malo-y-lo-peligroso-234725
September 2025	Not so demanding! Employing the Fuzzy-hybrid TOPSIS to explain (un)demanding whale-watcher behaviour	Chaitanya Suárez-Rojas, Yen E. Lam-González, Juan Carlos Martín	Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jort.2025.100919

Table 11. Scientific Publications.

4.7 Events

Members of the consortium have participated offline and online at different events to promote the project and extend the network. These are the actions and events that have taken place during the first 24 months of the project:

Partner	Type of event	Target group	Name	Location	Date	Link
TIDES-ULPGC, CETECIMA	Conference	Scientific community, Industry, Policy Makers	Impulso azul	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Spain)	06/06/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/03/twinnedbystars-to-participate-in-impulso-azul-on-june-6th-in-las-palmas/
TIDES-ULPGC	Conference	Scientific community, Industry, Policy makers	SSTD 2024	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Spain)	12-14/06/2024	https://tides.ulpgc.es/en/congreso-sstd/
Nautic Ocean	Tourism Fair	Civil Society and Industry	B-Travel	Barcelona (Spain)	16/03/2024	https://clusternautic.cat/2024/03/05/el-cluster-nautic-catala-i-12-empreses-associades-promouran-el-turisme-nautic-al-b-travel/
Nautic Ocean	Conference	Industry	The Art of Sailing	Barcelona (Spain)	01/04/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/04/01/the-art-of-

						sailing-is-presented-by-nautic-oceans/
Nautic Ocean	Conference	Industry	World Night	Barcelona (Spain)	15/04/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/04/18/nautic-oceans-unveils-commemorative-event-for-world-night-twinnedbystars-presentation/
Nautic Ocean	Conference	Civil Society, Industry	America's Cup 2024	Barcelona (Spain)	22/08/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/09/10/the-twinnedbystars-project-at-the-olympic-port-during-the-americas-cup-2024/
Nautic Ocean	Conference	Civil Society, Industry	Presentation of the book Diminuto Planeta Azul	Barcelona (Spain)	07/01/2025	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/01/09/twinnedbystars-was-presented-during-the-presentation-of-the-book-diminuto-planeta-azul-tiny-blue-planet/
CE, CMC, CETECIMA, ULPGC	Fair	Civil Society, Industry	FIMAR 2024 (International Sea Fair)	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain	8-10/06/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/11/twinnedbystar-shines-at-fimar-2024-a-boost-for-the-blue-economy/
CE	Conference	Industry	KOM A3MAtlantic Project	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain	29/01/2025	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/01/29/twinnedbystars-strengthens-its-impact-by-participating-in-the-kick-off-meeting-of-the-a3matlantic-project/
EBI, CE, CMC	Fair	Policy makers, Industry, Scientific Community	European Maritime Days 2025	Cork, Ireland	21 - 23/05/2025	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/05/27/twinnedbystars-boosts-the-debate-on-maritime-and-coastal-tourism-in-the-outermost-regions-at-the-european-maritime-day-in-cork/
CETECIMA	Conference	Civil Society, Industry	Atlantic Week 2024	Bordeaux, France	20 - 22/11/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/11/22/cetecima-participates-in-the-atlantic-week-2024-in-bordeaux/

TWINNEDby STARS consortium	EU event	Policy makers, Industry, Scientific Community	European Oceans Days - Poster presentation	Brussels, Belgium	03/06/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/03/15/discovering-the-ocean-at-european-oceans-days/
EBI, CMC	Conference	Policy makers, Industry, Scientific Community	European Maritime Day 2024	Svendborg, Denmark	30-31/05/2024	https://maritime-day.ec.europa.eu/index_en
CMC	Conference	Industry	XIX Symposium on Marinas	Getxo, Bizkaia, Spain	25-26/04/2024	www.simposiopuertosdeportivos.es
CTM	Conference	Policy makers	The cultural, touristic and scientific sites in Martinique	Hôtel de l'Assemblée Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique	27/03/2024	N/A
CTM	Fair	Industry	Martinique Boat Show	Port de Plaisance, Fort de France	30/05/2024-02/06/2024	https://www.martinique-boat-show.fr/
ACIF	Fair	Industry	Expo Madeira	Estádio do marítimo, Madeira, Portugal	04/07/2025 – 13/07/2025	https://www.acif-ccim.pt/expomadeira-2025/?doing_wp_cron=1756200667.2302570343017578125000

Table 12. Attended events by TWINNEDbySTARS Consortium.

At the same time, the project has promoted the organization of its own dissemination events.

In 2024, the ‘Stellar Tour’ was a virtual journey designed for young Europeans that allowed them to explore constellations and astronomical mythologies from the regions of the Canaries, Azores, Madeira, and Martinique.

In the same year, a series of five masterclasses was held exclusively for members of our community. These masterclasses benefitted 55 small and medium-sized companies in the maritime tourism sector, offering training in local languages (2 in Spanish, 2 in Portuguese, and 1 in French) in astro tourism and digital strategies to attract customers, with the aim of providing key tools for the development and innovation of companies in the sector.

In the same year, nautical tourism companies, researchers and public institutions from the Canary Islands (Spain) and Viana do Castelo (Portugal) came together at the Impulso Azul event to explore current barriers to green growth and identify synergies between both regions. This gathering served as a valuable platform to address key challenges and opportunities in the field of sustainable nautical tourism.

The fourth co-creation workshop of the TWINNEDbySTARS project was held during the last quarter of 2024. This face-to-face meeting brought together local companies and experts from the nautical tourism sector, together with invited companies from other regions and project partners, with the aim of jointly advancing in the design of innovative tourism products.

In 2025, as part of the objective set out in task 2.2 of the TWINNEDbySTARS project, a total of 13 online training courses have been delivered, focusing on the use of artificial intelligence in digital communication and the Marine Starlight initiative. These sessions have provided participating companies with practical tools to optimise their digital strategy and better understand the potential of the night sky as a tourist resource, thus contributing to innovation and differentiation of their offerings within the nautical sector.

In addition, the practical part related to Marine Starlight has been carried out in person in two of the outermost regions (Azores and Madeira) participating in the project, allowing companies to apply the knowledge acquired directly in the field and explore new opportunities for creating nautical experiences linked to night sky observation. The practical part of Marine Starlight is expected to be completed in Gran Canaria and Martinique in October 2025. Likewise, the practical training for Hydrphone Training will be given in Martinique, also in October 2025.

Partner organisations	Type of event	Target group	Name	Location	Date	Link
ULPGC-TIDES, CE, CMC, CETECIMA	Conference	Civil society, policy makers, industry, scientific community	Open Event to project kick off meeting	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	26/10/2023	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2023/11/02/twinned-by-stars-business-meeting-experiences-at-sea-people-that-inspire/
ULPGC-TIDES, Nautic Ocean, CE	Conference Online	Civil society	Stellar Tour (EMD in my Country)	Online	16/05/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/22/the-stellar-tours-event-ends-with-success/
ULPGC-TIDES, Nautic Ocean, CE	Training	Industry	Masterclass on astro tourism and sailing for SMEs in the Canary Islands	Online	20/06/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/07/18/successful-completion-of-the-masterclass-sessions-for-smes-in-the-maritime-tourism-sector/
			Masterclass on Experimentation and Online Tactics to Attract More Customers for Azorean and Madeira SMEs		26/06/2024	
			Masterclass on Experimentation and Online Tactics to Attract More Customers for SMEs in the Canaries		28/06/2024	
			Masterclass on astro tourism and sailing for Azorean and Madeira SMEs		01/07/2024	

			Masterclass on Experimentation and Online Tactics to Attract More Customers for Martinique's SMEs		17/07/2024	
CMC	Workshop	Other	Encuentro Impulso azul	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain	06/06/2024	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7203326551537369088?updateEntityUrn=urn%3A%3A%28V2%2Curn%3A%3A%3Aactivity%3A7203326551537369088%29
TWINNEDby STARS Consortium	Workshop	Industry	Co-Creation Workshops	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain	23-24/09/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/09/24/twinnedbystars-brings-together-experts-and-smes-from-the-maritime-tourism-and-nautical-sector-in-las-palmas-de-gran-canaria/
				Madeira, Portugal	23-24/10/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/10/25/madeira-hosts-the-second-twinnedbystars-co-creation-workshop/
				Online	13-14/11/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/11/15/successful-co-creation-workshop-in-martinique-drives-synergies-in-the-twinnedbystars-community/
				Faial, Azores, Portugal	28/11/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/11/29/twinnedbystars-held-its-project-meeting-and-last-co-creation-workshop-in-faial/
Nautic Ocean	Conference	Citizens	Presentation of the book Diminuto Planeta Azul by Javier Ares	Barcelona, Spain	07/01/2025	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/01/09/twinnedbystars-was-presented-during-the-presentation-of-the-book-diminuto-

						planeta-azul-tiny-blue-planet/
ULPGC – TIDES & CE	Trainings	Industry	Use of AI in Digital Communication for Nautical Tourism	Online	18 & 25/03/2025	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/02/21/twinnedbystars-launches-two-free-courses-on-artificial-intelligence-for-the-nautical-sector/
			Your Digital Compass: AI for successful social media navigation		04 & 11/04/2025	
ULPGC-TIDES, NAUTIC OCEAN, & CE	Trainings	Industry	(Marine Starguide training) - History of astronomy	Online	22/04/2025	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/04/14/registration-is-now-open-for-the-sea-starlight-monitor-training-course-for-nautical-companies-interested-in-astro-tourism/
			(Marine Starguide training) - Measuring spacetime			
			(Marine Starguide training) - Basic Astronomy Course		23/04/2025	
			(Marine Starguide training) - The Solar System			
			(Marine Starguide training) - How to find your way around the sky		24/04/2025	
			(Marine Starguide training) - Preparing an observation with Stellarium			
			(Marine Starguide training) - Nautical astro-tourism marketing and communication skills		29/04/2025	
			(Marine Starguide training) - Light pollution		30/04/2025	
			(Marine Starguide training) - Mythology in			

			astronomical navigation			
			(Marine Starguide training) - History of navigation			
			(Marine Starguide training) - Astronomical tourism and the role of Starlight certification		07/05/2025	
ULPGC – TIDES- Nautic Ocean, DPRM, Marina do Funchal, ACIF-CIMM	Trainings	Industry	Practical Marine Starguide training	The Azores, Portugal	15/06/2025	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2025/06/17/the-practical-phase-of-the-marine-starguide-certification-takes-place-in-azores-and-madeira/
				Madeira, Portugal	16/06/2025	

Table 13. Events organised by TWINNEDbySTARS

4.8 Advertising campaigns

4.8.1 STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT CAMPAIGN

As part of the stakeholder engagement activities promoted through WP1, a digital campaign targeting nautical and maritime SMEs was launched in four specific regions under WP5. The objective of the campaign was to capture the interest of businesses, policymakers, associations, and decision-makers and invite them to join this innovative network.

Moreover, the aim was to engage these businesses and motivate them to participate in strategic surveys to collect relevant information to share other relevant project activities, such as WP3 co-creation workshops and WP2 trainings. To this end, the WP5 campaign designed and used social media posts, posters and online banners.

Two surveys were designed and promoted among enterprises in each of the 4 regions, which are intended to gather essential information for capacity building and the creation of collaborative tourism products:

- Survey #1 – Introductory questionnaire to engage companies: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/TWINNEDbySTARSQuestionnaire>
- Survey #2 – Detailed questionnaire to gather information on companies' activity, needs, and challenges: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/twinned-for-smes>

The surveys and many of the posters, publications, and banners were translated into the local languages of the participating regions to ensure greater inclusiveness and effectiveness of communication. In addition, all materials were designed to be inclusive, gender-balanced, reflect social diversity, and represent people with disabilities appropriately.

Figure 25. Poster for stakeholder engagement campaign.

Figure 26. social media campaign for stakeholder engagement.

Figure 27. Banner for stakeholder engagement campaign.

In the campaign that was designed to reach out to companies and encourage them to fill out the project surveys, Meta Ads were implemented, generating a total of 55,933 impressions and 15,420 views. Through these ads, 276 people clicked on the link to participate in the survey. During the campaign period, approximately 20 enterprises signed up for the survey thanks to the Facebook Ads.

Figure 27. social media campaign for stakeholder engagement.

4.8.2 SME CAMPAIGN MASTERCLASS

To reward the companies for their participation in the TWINNEDbySTARS project and to maximise the value of their involvement, **a series of free masterclasses were organised by the consortium and offered to the involved companies.** These sessions were specifically designed to provide them with valuable and practical knowledge that would enrich the value of their business.

The TWINNEDbySTARS masterclasses focused on key topics to boost the growth of SMEs in the maritime tourism sector. In the first one, entitled 'Experimentation and Online Tactics to Attract More Customers', participants learnt digital marketing strategies and innovative techniques to attract customers online, focusing on stargazing activities and obtaining Starlight certification,

which allowed them to diversify their nautical offer. The second one, 'Astrotourism and its Potential for Your Business', highlighted the opportunities offered by astrotourism to deseasonalize demand, expand nautical services, and obtain Starlight certification, generating greater value for businesses. Both sessions pointed to charter, sailing, catamaran, whale watching, and scuba diving companies.

The campaign to promote these masterclasses, conducted under WP5, included a variety of strategies. Content was posted on social media, which included short clips of the recorded sessions, encouraging companies to become part of the enterprise network of TWINNEDbySTARS. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C8rVhwjCm1x/>

In addition, an email campaign was launched for companies in the sector, inviting them to participate in the masterclasses. These emails provided details on the agenda and topics to be addressed and highlighted how companies could use the knowledge gained to boost their business. These emails were sent in local languages to ensure communication. Following the masterclasses, full recordings were sent to the companies so that they could review the content at their own pace

Figure 28. Email invitation to the Masterclasses

To access these sessions, companies first had to complete Stakeholder Engagement campaign survey designed to collect strategic data that would support capacity building and tourism product creation.

With this campaign, TWINNEDbySTARS not only rewarded the companies for their participation, but also provided them with valuable tools to further their growth and diversification in the maritime tourism sector.

4.8.3 STELLAR TOUR SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN

In the framework of European Maritime Days in My Country, the 'Stellar Tour', a virtual experience for young Europeans interested in the cosmos and astronomy, was promoted. The event, which took place on 16 May 2024, included an online journey through the Canary Islands, Azores, Madeira and Martinique while exploring constellations, mythologies and astronomical curiosities. Participants discovered the history and meaning of the constellations over the course of 40 minutes, as well as the astronomical interpretations of ancient European cultures.

Figure 29. Stellar Tour online event

A social media campaign strategy including Instagram posts and stories was implemented to promote this event to reach out civil society and younger audiences. The content was aimed at attracting the attention of young Europeans, highlighting interesting aspects of the event and providing some basic knowledge. The target audience for this strategy had interests in astronomy and maritime ecotourism, as well as enthusiasm and participation.

The event was attended online by 49 participants.

Figure 30. Post of Social Media Campaign for Stellar Tour.

In the Instagram Stories, a star quiz was created and designed to capture the interest and participation of the young audience. The Instagram stories included two key questions related to the event themes. The following day, a video explanation was posted.

Quiz	Question	Answer
Quiz 1	What is the relationship between mythology and the constellations Ursa Major and Ursa Minor?	<p>A) They are constellations that represent gods and goddesses in Greek mythology.</p> <p>B) They are constellations that play an important role in the legends and myths of different cultures.</p> <p>C) They are constellations that serve as a guide for travellers on the high seas.</p> <p>D) They are constellations that symbolise the creation of the universe in Norse mythology.</p>
Quiz 2	Which star in Orion's Belt helps us to know east and west?	<p>A) Rigel</p> <p>B) Betelgeuse</p> <p>C) Bellatrix</p> <p>D) Mintaka</p>

Table 14. Star Quiz.

These Instagram stories not only informed participants about what they could learn at the event, but also actively engaged them in the astronomical theme of the Stellar Tour, building anticipation and excitement leading up to the event.

Figure 31. Stories of Social Media Campaign for Stellar Tour.

4.9 Videos

4.9.1 OFFICIAL ANIMATED VIDEO

An official animated presentation video illustrating the objectives, challenges, partners and work packages of the TWINNEDbySTARS project is being produced. The animation is being produced by Help Studio, while the voice-over was done by Bunny Studio App. The video is in English and subtitled in the local languages of each project region, including Spanish (ES), Portuguese (PT) and French (FR). The video will be available this autumn on the official TWINNEDbySTARS YouTube channel: www.youtube.com/@twinnedbystars

Dissemination Strategy:

After its launch, the video is promoted through a series of strategic actions to maximise its visibility. Firstly, through a social media reel to capture the attention of the audience and generate interactions with the YouTube channel. It is also housed on the TWINNEDbySTARS website to ensure its accessibility to all visitors. Project partners are encouraged to share the video on their official networks, thus extending its reach across their platforms. In addition, the video will be integrated into the various future events related to the project to reinforce its presence and promote its impact on each occasion, and finally, it is also available in the newsletter releases.

4.9.2 SHORT VIDEOS / REELS

From time to time, videos and testimonial reels are published on social networks showing the activities developed in the framework of the TWINNEDbySTARS project. These materials include interventions from consortium partners, explaining their contributions to the project, as well as testimonials from companies in the TWINNEDbySTARS community highlighting the benefits of being part of this collaborative network. In addition, videos are shared on activities carried out during the implementation of the project and content related to complementary initiatives, such as the sister project ECOROUTE.

Date	Title	Type of Video	Link
31/05/2024	EMD 2024	Project Activity	https://www.instagram.com/reel/C7oLOwEiCIC/
26/06/2024	Extract from the SME training masterclass in the tourism-maritime sector	Project Activity	https://www.instagram.com/reel/C8rVhwjCm1x/
27/06/2024	Extract from the training masterclass on experimentation and online tactics that we have given for tourism SMEs.	Project Activity	https://www.instagram.com/reel/C8t3FZ6ig2V/
02/09/2024	Testimonial from TIDES - ULPGC	Partners' testimony	https://www.instagram.com/reel/C_aekMcCHd8/
13/09/2024	Testimonial from Nautic Ocean	Partners' testimony	https://www.instagram.com/reel/C_22vfvjAbL/
30/09/2024	Testimonials from Astroeduca	Stakeholder Testimony	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DAicQMtlz9/
10/10/2024	Testimonials from XReality Factory's	Stakeholder Testimony	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DA8SG30IDv-/
18/10/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS Community Testimonial	Stakeholder Testimony	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DBQszDnCI3V/
29/11/2024	Last co-creation workshop in Faial, Azores	Project Activity	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DC82JnhobwE/
13/12/2024	Connecting Regions – Co-creation Workshops in TWINNEDbySTARS	Partners' testimony	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DDhjYwkCGEZ/
07/02/2025	TWINNEDbySTARS CONECTS BUSINESSES FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE IN NAUTICAL TOURISM	Partners' testimony	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DFxqvHaJXhi/
14/02/2025	What is it that our companies value?	Stakeholder Testimony	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DGDjlo2C9Yq/
19/02/2025	ECOROUTE: Sustainable routes for a better future	Testimonial from Sister Project	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DGQCBk1iTEv/
12/03/2025	Keep Sailing: From co-creation to starlight certification	Stakeholder Testimony	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DHGhRICCKQd/

21/03/2025	First starlight certified nautical company in the Canary Islands	Project Activity	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DHdh3GIIxxJ/
04/04/2025	TWINNEDbySTARS Trainings - Use of Artificial Intelligence in Digital Communication for Nautical Tourism	Project Activity	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DIBTeaHiGqP/
25/04/2025	Madeira Sunkiss sailing Certification	Stakeholder Testimony	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DI3REMCWir/
13/05/2025	TWINNEDbySTARS Trainings – Marine Starlight	Project Activity	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DJmGjaGokqP/
30/07/2025	Euronews report	Partner Testimony	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DMufXPkJ_4A/
05/08/2025		Stakeholder Testimony	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DM-kJzoBJBb/
12/08/2025		Stakeholder Testimony	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DNQG2r6IKHg/

Table 15. Short videos for social media.

4.10 Synergies with other projects/initiatives

On the TWINNEDbySTARS website and in the first two TWINNEDbySTARS newsletters, a specific section has been dedicated to related projects:

ECOROUTE

EcoRoute is a project dedicated to sustainable development in the Outermost Regions of the European Union. Its main objective is to transform these territories into smart destinations for nature and underwater cultural tourism, focusing on the design of sustainable strategies, the promotion of policy initiatives, and the strengthening of local community capacities. More information about the project is available at: <https://ecoroute.eu/>.

During the reporting period, **TWINNEDbySTARS** has developed several synergies with EcoRoute that have reinforced the common objectives of both projects. Among the most noteworthy is their joint participation in the *EuroNews Ocean* documentary, which provided international visibility to the initiatives of both. EcoRoute also took part in the latest co-creation session held in the Azores, where it shared its expertise to support the design of new tourism products within TWINNEDbySTARS. In addition, the project contributed to the debate on maritime and coastal tourism in the Outermost Regions during the *European Maritime Day* in Cork, enriching discussions on the future of the sector. EcoRoute will also collaborate in an underwater activity during the upcoming Steering Committee in Martinique, further strengthening the exchange of experiences between both projects in the field of sustainable maritime tourism.

These activities have strengthened collaboration between related European projects, enhancing the visibility of the Outermost Regions as laboratories of innovation in sustainable tourism.

SEA STARLIGHT

Sea Starlight is a national platform (in Spain) dedicated to offering exclusive nautical and astronomical experiences, combining activities along the Spanish coast, linking the sea with the starry sky. This initiative allows participants to enjoy sailing while discovering the mysteries of the universe through carefully guided astronomical observations. Learn more about the project at: <https://www.seastarlight.com/>.

During the reporting period, synergies have been reinforced between Sea Starlight and TWINNEDbySTARS through joint actions that connect nautical activities with starlight observation, thus contributing to the development of innovative tourism products within the project. Notably, Sea Starlight collaborated in the training of monitors organised by the Canary Islands Maritime Cluster in Gran Canaria, a capacity-building activity that provided specialised knowledge to professionals working in the maritime tourism sector. This cooperation not only strengthens the visibility of Sea Starlight within the framework of TWINNEDbySTARS but also supports the project's objective of promoting sustainable and differentiated tourism experiences in the Outermost Regions.

EUROPEAN MARITIME DAY (EMD)

European Maritime Day is the flagship initiative of the European Commission to promote dialogue and cooperation around the sustainable blue economy. TWINNEDbySTARS actively engaged with this initiative during the reporting period through different formats: the organisation of the Stellar Tour under EMD in My Country 2024, participation in the European Maritime Day 2024 in Svendborg (Denmark), and active contribution to the European Maritime Day 2025 held in Cork (Ireland). On this occasion, a joint workshop was organised together with the EcoRoute project, reinforcing synergies and enriching discussions on the future of sustainable maritime and coastal tourism in the Outermost Regions. These activities allowed the project to showcase its results, strengthen the visibility of the Outermost Regions in the European debate, and connect with other EU projects and stakeholders. This collaboration consolidates TWINNEDbySTARS' role as a reference initiative for innovative and sustainable tourism in the Outermost Regions.

MISSION RESTORE OUR OCEAN AND WATERS CHARTER

The European Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters" seeks to mobilise stakeholders around three core objectives: the protection and restoration of marine and freshwater ecosystems, the prevention and reduction of pollution, and the development of a sustainable, circular and carbon-neutral blue economy. TWINNEDbySTARS is currently working on its adherence to the Mission Charter by presenting its co-creation workshops as a concrete action contributing to these goals. These workshops brought together entrepreneurs and stakeholders from the Canary Islands, Madeira, Martinique and the Azores to collaboratively design innovative, sustainable and circular tourism products, with strong potential for replication in other regions. Through this process, the project fosters citizen participation, supports the diversification of tourism in the Outermost Regions, and raises awareness about the link between sustainable tourism and environmental protection.

A3MATLANTIC

A3MAtlantic is a project that seeks to promote innovation and internationalisation among SMEs in the mid-Atlantic regions involved in the blue economy, through the implementation of pilot actions and joint solutions promoted by the quadruple helix within the A3M Alliance. The initiative aims to strengthen the governance of the alliance by extending its scope beyond the MAC territories, capitalising on the results obtained in the previous SMARTBLUE and SMARTBLUE_F projects and generating a strategic agenda that positions these regions at the heart of European and international decision-making. Its activities include raising awareness and supporting SMEs,

developing training skills (upskilling, reskilling and cross-skilling), internationalising mature and emerging sectors of the blue economy, and promoting transnational and cross-border business cooperation.

TWINNEDbySTARS' participation in the launch of A3MAtlantic has enabled it to establish strategic connections with members of the A3M Alliance, share best practices in nautical and collaborative tourism, and explore joint opportunities with the ATLAZUL project. This collaboration reinforces TWINNEDbySTARS' commitment to the blue economy and the internationalisation of SMEs in the maritime sector, while helping to position the outermost regions as leaders in innovation and sustainability within the European context.

The plan for the final project phase of TWINNEDbySTARS under WP5 is to keep the contacts with the projects ongoing and assess additional potential collaborations in terms of joint events, policy recommendations, and results' sharing initiatives.

CALLMEBLUE

Maritime clusters play a vital role in connecting public and private entities within the blue economy, fostering networking, technology transfer and innovation. The CALLMEBLUE project aims to strengthen cluster alliances in the Mediterranean, fostering North-South and South-South cooperation. By raising awareness and implementing concrete actions, including training programmes, the project strives to improve the sustainability of blue economy policies. Ultimately, CALLMEBLUE aims to strengthen the role of maritime clusters in fostering regional cooperation and supporting initiatives such as the UfM Ministerial Declaration and the WestMED Initiative. Find out more about the project at: <https://callme-blue.eu/>.

MSP-OR

MSP-OR, is a project focused on maritime spatial planning (MSP). It supports competent authorities in the implementation of the EU MSP Directive (2014/89/EU), promoting its implementation in the outermost regions of the Azores, Madeira, the Canary Islands and French Guiana. Through this approach, MSP-OR contributes to more effective ocean governance, applying the Ecosystem Based Approach to ensure sustainable and well-planned maritime development. More information about the project at: <https://msp-or.eu/>

FISATUR

FISATUR is a project designed to boost the economic growth of coastal fishing regions. This project is closely linked to the local fisheries and tourism sectors, seeking the effective integration and promotion of Atlantic tourism products and services related to fisheries, aquaculture and maritime heritage. The objective of FISATUR is to evaluate and promote an innovative model of fishery-maritime tourism. This approach has the potential to transform the way we think about and use coastal resources, opening up new opportunities for sustainable economic development in these regions. Find out more about this project at: <https://www.fisatur.org/>

So far, TWINNEDbySTARS has established and nurtured contacts with a wide range of related initiatives, creating opportunities for mutual visibility, knowledge sharing and joint actions. These collaborations —ranging from European projects such as EcoRoute, Sea Starlight, A3MAtlantic, to European Commission initiatives like the European Maritime Day and the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters Charter— have strengthened the role of the Outermost Regions as laboratories of innovation in sustainable maritime and coastal tourism.

Building on this momentum, the last year of work of the project will focus on consolidating these partnerships through policy recommendations and result-sharing activities, ensuring that

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TWINNEDbySTARS continues to contribute to a wider European and international dialogue on the future of the blue economy.

Figure 32. TWINNEDbySTARS coordinator presenting the project at the Ecoroute meeting.

Figure 33. TWINNEDbySTARS representative presenting the project at the A3M Atlantic meeting.

5. RESULTS AND EVALUATION OF DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Monitoring of the activities allows to assess if the actions planned are carried out properly and on time and to measure their effectiveness. Based on monitoring results, the project D&C Plan might be thus reformulated to improve the communication and dissemination outreach.

To monitor the project, partners are periodically requested to provide information on the activities carried out (for instance organisation of events, publications of news/press releases, etc., presentations at conferences) while CE is in charge of monitoring and reporting on the use of the website, social media, and on the events whose organisation is under CE's responsibility. Based on the reports submitted from the partners, CE can formulate recommendations for the future dissemination and communication activities.

See below the achieved results of the dissemination and communication actions carried out during the first 24 months of the project are shown below:

Indicator	Targets set in the D&C Plan	Results (M1-M24)
Participation of regional/national/EU events	10	17
Organisation of project own events/webinars/masterclasses	10	24
Production of newsletters	6	4
Total newsletter subscribers	300	396
N° of press releases	9	32 (1 international, 2 national, 26 regional (1 journal, 16 online press and 5 radio, 4 TV))
Website unique visits	3000	3500
Total followers (LinkedIn, X, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube)	1000	1067
Scientific publications	1	3
Videos produced	1 animated video + at least 10 short videos/reels	1 animated video and 21 short videos/reels

Table 16. Monitoring and evaluation indicators' progress at M24.

The progress and impact of the D&C actions will be evaluated in the final D&C report (M35) to provide a clearer understanding of the project's overall impact and visibility.

6. Conclusions and recommendations

This report summarises the dissemination and communication activities carried out during the first 24 months of the TWINNEDbySTARS project. The WP5 leader, in collaboration with all project partners, has been actively involved in the development and launch of materials and the implementation of associated activities in accordance with the strategy outlined in the TWINNEDbySTARS [Dissemination and Communication Plan \(D5.1\)](#).

Each communication and dissemination initiative has been designed to achieve specific objectives and address the project's key stakeholders, working in close cooperation with the WP1 Stakeholder Engagement Plan, and using various communication tools, including brochures, roll-ups and customised templates, to ensure a consistent message and a cohesive visual identity for the target audience.

Stakeholders have been regularly updated on the progress of TWINNEDbySTARS through the project website, events, social media channels, events, and newsletters.

Partners have been actively involved in project dissemination, with a special focus on the expansion of the TWINNEDbySTARS business network in the context of the product creation and capacity building activities foreseen in WP2 and WP3. The dissemination at local level has

allowed TWINNEDbySTARS to contact specific stakeholders and to identify several companies interested and committed to participate in the different phases of the project.

It is relevant to underline that the project has achieved media coverage also thanks to the support of CINEA. The Agency has supported the dissemination of the project through the publication of several contents on its social networks and the inclusion of the first webinar, 'Stellar Tour', in the playlist of its YouTube channel, dedicated to the areas of Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture. It can be viewed at the following link:

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLrp3luGqStFAjpbU4i7Y5-vIIFLKGnoQV>

In addition, partnerships and contacts with related initiatives and projects have been established to further promote TWINNEDbySTARS (sister projects). The next step for WP5 will be to assess future joint collaborations in order to strengthen stakeholder involvement and maximise the exploitation of results with similar initiatives.

Finally, dissemination and communication activities are progressing according to plan. The next phase of WP5 will focus on optimising the results achieved so far, with emphasis on promoting more technical activities related to the next milestones of TWINNEDbySTARS. In particular, over the next year, special attention will be paid to the increase of social media followers, the promotion of additional dissemination events and synergies with relevant projects and initiatives at EU and OR levels.

In fact, WP5 has provided crucial support to WP2 and WP3, both by promoting and disseminating the training activities addressed to SMEs and by giving wide visibility to the co-created products and the selected project product. These actions have ensured strong participation across the four regions and maximised the impact of the project's innovation and capacity-building efforts. At the same time, WP5 has played a strategic role in positioning TWINNEDbySTARS within the European debate on sustainable maritime and coastal tourism, through contributions to the European Maritime Day, the Euronews Ocean documentary, and the forthcoming adherence to the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters Charter. This has reinforced the visibility of the Outermost Regions as laboratories of innovation, while opening the way for new synergies and collaborations at both EU and international levels.

TWINNED

By Stars

Unlocking the potential of innovation, circularity, and digitalisation for accelerating new marine-based ecotourism, joint practices, and businesses in ORs

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